

COMMON MISTAKES IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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Annotation: In the past and in the present, language learners have faced many challenges in learning English. They also made many mistakes. But making mistakes encourages a person to learn and search more. Therefore, you should not be afraid of making mistakes. And you should continue to learn new knowledge. This article explains about such mistakes, difficulties, and misunderstandings one by one, and tries to explain with examples as much as possible.

Keywords: English language, grammar, grammatical mistakes, speaking, spelling, listening, tenses, preposition, lexic mistakes, certificate, language learner, word order, foreign countries, young people, new vocabulary

As we all know, English is the most widely spoken language in the world today. We can easily say that this language is the language of international communication. Because now almost 90 percent of people can communicate in English. That's why it has become very important to know English. Even when applying to study somewhere or getting a job, they are asked to know English. That's why today's young people make learning this language one of their main goals..

Learning a language is not an easy task. Learning a language also has its own difficulties. That is why, a person who is learning a language should first be patient and patient. Then The language learner can achieve his goal. Only if he or she can overcome the difficulties and problems that arise in front of him. In addition, we can say that today's young people are forced to learn English. Because if they get a certificate of knowledge of the English language, they can achieve high results in entrance exams. Or they can apply to foreign universities with a certificate of language proficiency. Such reasons encourage young people to set wrong goals for themselves. If the goal is not clear, it becomes much more difficult to achieve it. Because young people have put getting a certificate in the first place in their minds. Instead of learning a language, they are trying to get a certificate. Learning becomes more difficult. Therefore, when learning a language, one should learn it at will...

Also, one of the main mistakes in learning English is to study only grammar for a long time. This has a negative effect on the speaking ability of the person learning the language. As a result, the student's speaking skills will not develop well. As a result, that person memorizes a lot of vocabulary in order to improve and develop his speaking skills. But this learning method does not help the person learning the language, on the contrary, it makes it very difficult to learn the language. Therefore, even if he does not learn English grammar very well, even if he makes mistakes, it will be more useful for him to speak more, only speaking skills will grow a lot. If there is an opportunity to advise them, a person learning a language should talk with native speakers, only then the speaking skill will grow a lot..

Additionally, one of the many mistakes in learning English is spelling mistakes. That is, a language learner can make a number of spelling mistakes when writing. He can write down what he hears. But in English, words are pronounced differently and written differently. That's why When memorizing words, you need to pay attention. For example, the simple word "Wednesday" is pronounced as [wenesday], that is, the letter [d] in this word is not pronounced, but written. This is one of the simplest examples of mistakes in spelling. But there are millions of such words in English. Therefore, in order not to make mistakes in spelling, you need to memorize and understand each one carefully.

Speaking of other mistakes you can make, these are the mistakes you'll encounter when learning English grammar. As an example, we can say that there may be situations such as incorrect use of tenses, confusion of prepositions when composing a sentence. If all the above-mentioned cases are thoroughly studied, the difficulties of the language learner will be reduced considerably. And he will try not to make mistakes.

Another common mistake is lexical errors. That is, a lexical error can occur as a result of using the wrong word that does not fit in a sentence or text. If a lexical error is made, the content of the sentence and its meaning will change. It is necessary to understand its dictionary and lexical meaning and then use it. If all the above-mentioned cases are thoroughly studied, the difficulties of the language learner will be reduced considerably. And he will try not to make mistakes.

In conclusion , learning a language is a very difficult process. But there are people who overcome all difficulties and learn a language with patience. They can make a lot of mistakes during language learning. Those mistakes help them to develop and learn the language well. That's why every People who are learning new knowledge should never be afraid. If they have a little patience, they will achieve their goal.

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